

Sustainable 6G Architecture: An organic evolution of 5G networks

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Abstract

The evolution of cellular networks towards 6G presents an opportunity to enhance not only coverage and capacity **but also environmental, social, and economic sustainability**. This paper proposes a sustainable cloud-native and modular 6G architecture that integrates AI-driven resource orchestration and intent-based network management. The proposed design introduces a modular approach where network functions are structured into adaptable building blocks, allowing for seamless scalability and flexible deployment tailored to emerging use cases. AI is embedded across multiple layers to optimize energy efficiency, improve service accessibility, and enable intelligent decision-making. Furthermore, the architecture leverages integrated network-compute paradigms, enhancing service placement efficiency and minimizing energy consumption through optimized edge computing solutions. Intent-based management further refines network operations by shifting from manual configurations to high-level policy abstractions, improving

resource efficiency while reducing operational complexity. This paper also explores enhancements to both the Radio Access Network (RAN) and Core Network (CN), improving network modularization and signaling efficiency. The proposed framework ensures a smooth transition from 5G to 6G while addressing key challenges such as network sustainability, trustworthiness, and digital inclusivity. By incorporating these elements, the envisioned 6G architecture aims to establish a resilient, energy-efficient, and future-proof network ecosystem.

Keywords: 6G, SBA, network virtualization, network modularization, flexibility, efficiency

1. Introduction

When designing or building new systems and applications, [such as 6G](#), sustainability, i.e., "meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to [meet](#) their needs" [1], is important. Sustainability encompasses three key dimensions, interconnected and influenced by each [other, i.e.](#), environmental, social, and economic sustainability [2]. Environmental sustainability demands optimization in network energy consumption, device life-cycle, and carbon footprint. Social sustainability requires ensuring that 6G networks and services are accessible to everyone, regardless of location, while prioritizing [cybersecurity](#) and data privacy. Economic sustainability involves developing innovative business models that prioritize long-term sustainability. These principles must be considered at every stage of the 6G design process to ensure a truly sustainable future. However, meeting the requirements of one dimension may sometimes come at the cost of another. Therefore, the 6G design requires considering and balancing all three aspects of sustainability. This means designing networks that minimize their environmental impact, promote digital inclusion and trustworthiness, and are economically viable while promoting sustainable business practices[2].

To ensure [economic](#) viability, a large set of new use cases [is](#) envisioned for 6G, such as sensing, autonomous collaborative robots in a factory environment, and real-time digital twins. However, all these use cases require substantial compute resources (and edge computing), and in many cases, compute offloading from devices. Furthermore, for most 6G use cases, AI can be applied to meet their requirements. These new 6G services and their use

cases require a 6G architecture that is flexible, secure, modular, simple, and cloud-native. Designing such an architecture presents a significant challenge. A key goal is to achieve a common cloud-native approach across both the Radio Access Network (RAN) and the Core Network (CN), enabling seamless integration and scalability. However, many use cases will require only specific parts of the full architecture, making a modular approach essential. This modularity allows for cost-effective deployments tailored to specific verticals or applications, while still allowing future expansion into a complete 6G network as needed. This incremental scaling also facilitates a smooth migration from 5G to 6G, starting with specific customer offerings and use cases. To achieve this, a “modular architecture” is needed, i.e., consisting of easily deployable and scalable building blocks that allow plug-and-play deployments capable of adapting to changing demands. This modularity ensures flexibility without increasing complexity, allowing the network to scale to current needs.

This paper proposes architecture enhancements for security, intelligence, and flexibility. It uses a cloud native approach, applying it consistently across both the Radio Access Network (RAN) and the Core Network (CN). This architecture promotes a modular design that allows gradual growth and scalability. Network functions (NFs) are grouped into “modules,” which act as building blocks, enabling plug-and-play deployments that can adapt to changing demands. Modules are defined as groups of NFs, service providers, and consumers, and most interactions occur within the module itself. Communication between modules for a given procedure is minimized, allowing for efficient operation. Modules can be nested, and larger modules contain smaller ones. Furthermore, modules are designed to adapt to different execution environments and adjust their configurations accordingly. This adaptability leads to a redefinition of key interfaces, both horizontal (e.g., between RAN and core, or between different RANs) and vertical, based on the specific capabilities of the modules and the radio access technologies used.

2. 6G Key Value Indicators

The transition from 5G to 6G is not just about improving network performance; it represents a fundamental shift towards a more sustainable, inclusive, and intelligent digital ecosystem. Whereas previous generations generally prioritized technical metrics such as data rate and latency, 6G introduces a broader perspective, integrating environmental, social, and economic sus-

tainability into network design. Driven by global sustainability imperatives, such as digital inclusion agendas and emerging demands introduced by new services, e.g., immersive extended reality (XR) and intelligent IoT, 6G research has introduced KVIs to complement traditional performance KPIs. International frameworks (such as ITU’s IMT-2030) explicitly call out sustainability, ubiquitous intelligence, security/resilience, and connecting the unconnected as central design drivers for 6G [3]. In essence, KVIs ensure that as network capabilities evolve (e.g., integrating sensing, AI, and computing), they do so in alignment with essential human and societal needs.

Several forces control the selection of 6G KVIs. Sustainability is paramount in light of climate change and energy concerns: Next-generation networks are expected to be far more energy-efficient and carbon-neutral, addressing the ICT sector’s environmental footprint [4]. This involves not only “greening” the network itself (reducing power consumption and emissions) but also using 6G as an enabler for sustainable solutions across industries (the network’s “handprint” toward UN sustainability goals) [5]. Trustworthiness, which extends beyond security and privacy considerations, encompassing several aspects regarding the reliability of the networks, has become equally critical, as 6G will support ubiquitous intelligent services handling sensitive data. Ensuring robust and privacy-preserving mechanisms is essential to maintain user trust and safety. Meanwhile, digital inclusion is a key value recognizing that 5G still has not bridged the digital divide. 6G aims to provide connectivity everywhere at an affordable cost, extending access to remote and underserved communities to enable education, healthcare, and economic opportunities for all [6]. These KVIs, i.e., sustainability, trustworthiness, and inclusion, have been explicitly highlighted in 6G roadmaps as drivers for network evolution, reflecting societal demands and the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) for climate action, industry innovation, and reduced inequalities. Importantly, researchers note that pursuing these values will require balancing them with conventional KPIs: for example, densifying networks to improve coverage or [positioning accuracy](#) can undermine sustainability or affordability, while prioritizing security may introduce [latency–trade-offs](#) that must be managed. However, there are promising synergies – for instance, using accurate location information can improve energy efficiency (supporting sustainability) and broaden coverage to promote inclusiveness. A core challenge in 6G design is thus to integrate KVIs alongside technical KPIs in a way that advances performance and societal objectives in unison [3].

To effectively capture the three KVIs (sustainability, trustworthiness, and

inclusion) in the 6G/5GA architecture, it is essential to establish a structured approach that links these values to concrete design enablers. The evolution toward 6G is driven by the convergence of AI-driven decision-making, distributed computing paradigms, and robust security frameworks [7]. From a sustainability perspective, distributing intelligence across the network, from user equipment (UE) to edge nodes and central cloud, enables dynamic workload balancing that reduces power consumption. Such decentralized deployments also allow the network to flexibly scale resources where traffic demands are low, thereby minimizing the carbon footprint through targeted hardware utilization. Equally crucial for 6G is the expanded notion of trustworthiness, which goes beyond straightforward security considerations to include continuous verification, confidentiality, and resilience. Central to this vision is the zero-trust principle, where every network element, from infrastructure components to end-user devices, must be authenticated and authorized based on dynamic context rather than fixed credentials. Confidential computing further reinforces this strategy, keeping data encrypted during processing to maintain security and privacy in shared environments. At the same time, federated intelligence distributed throughout edge, cloud, and core layers enables real-time threat detection and mitigation through privacy-preserving AI, preventing the need to expose raw data. By weaving these layers together, 6G architectures can deliver robust resilience while ensuring persistent reliability. Finally, fostering inclusion relies on flexible service provisioning and edge intelligence that reduce latency and bring advanced capabilities, such as immersive XR or real-time IoT services, closer to remote areas. A compute-continuum approach, where resources are coordinated under Integrated Network and Compute (INC) paradigms, further supports underserved communities by allowing them to benefit from AI-driven decisions without requiring large-scale local infrastructure. Together, these architectural enablers, from AI-based resource orchestration to zero-trust security models and integrated cloud-edge coordination, reinforce each other to embody the core KVIs of sustainability, trustworthiness, and inclusion in the 6G/5GA vision.

3. 5G System evaluation

To motivate the selected architectural enablers, in the following, we analyse the sustainability of [the](#) current 5G network design, based on [the](#) local 5G network deployment energy consumption.

3.1. RAN Energy savings in 5G

The RAN is a key area for energy savings in mobile networks, as it is the main [energy-consuming](#) entity in 3GPP networks [8]. This is due to the network design principles, such as targeting the peak usage, which causes the radio resources to remain idle for most of the day. Moreover, regardless of the number of users, the active elements of the RAN [need](#) to be kept active even in low or no traffic scenarios. Consequently, [the](#) main gains in the RAN energy optimization are usually achieved by targeting low to medium load intervals, in addition to coordinating the energy savings with the core [9]. Three primary energy-saving strategies are being employed in the 5G Access Network (5G-AN), which can be effective in various network states [10]:

- Utilizing more power-efficient base stations and radio frequency (RF) hardware directly reduces energy consumption.
- Optimizing radio configurations and design to minimize unnecessary transmissions, i.e., cell sleep mode.
- Adapting allocated radio resources and deactivation of unnecessary resources, achieving energy savings when peak capacity is not required, e.g., dynamic massive Multiple Input Multiple Output (MIMO) muting and transmit power adaptations [11].

The 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) is actively developing new RAN energy-saving techniques in Release 18 and Release 19 of 5G-Advanced. Research indicates that by deploying the enhancements of Release 18, extensive energy savings can be [achieved](#) during low to medium load conditions [8].

3.2. Resource usage of CN functions during the 5G Registration Procedure

[As research on 6G networks takes on the challenge of reducing energy consumption, measuring energy consumption baselines today in the 5G system becomes necessary for future evaluations and improvements in environmental sustainability \[12\].](#) Therefore, the resource and energy consumption of individual 5G CN elements can be valuable parameters for efficient resource distribution throughout the cloud-continuum environment. This contribution focuses on providing insights into the efficiency of different parts of the CN by monitoring resources (CPU, memory) and energy usage of cloud-native network functions. These insights can be further analyzed to pinpoint

Figure 1: Experimental Test Bed.

parts of the CN that use disproportionate amounts of energy and improve their efficiency as input for the implementation of 6G.

Kepler, which stands for Kubernetes-based Efficient Power Level Exporter [13], is a project that focuses on providing a measurement of power consumption, which is then exported and stored in Prometheus [14]. Depending on the environment, when possible, the tool can provide separate power usage statistics for CPU, memory, and GPU. Then Kepler can estimate the energy consumption per process [15], which is assigned to a Kubernetes [16] container in a pod. Compatibility with Kubernetes allows monitoring the energy usage of different implementations of the 5G CN, making it easier to compare and improve existing projects.

The most popular open-source 5G Core implementations are Free5GC [17], Open5GS [18], and the OAI (OpenAirInterface) 5G CN [19]. Among these projects, we will find several distinct differences, such as the language in which they are implemented and their choice of database to store subscriber data. These differences affect their performance and efficiency, which have been analyzed in several studies [20],[21],[22]. For example, in one study [21], when comparing the total time taken to complete the registration and de-registration procedures for a UE, Open5GS leads in performance with Free5GC trailing right behind, while OAI 5G Core achieved the worst result.

In the literature, Open5GS consistently requires fewer CPU resources to achieve similar or shorter time results to complete UE registration and PDU

establishment procedures than Free5GC [20],[21],[22]. When it comes to data plane performance, in the study [20] Free5GC achieved much higher throughput than Open5GS; however, when limiting the number of virtual cores and RAM for the experiment, the gap in data plane performance became significantly smaller. The authors of [20] note that Open5GS has up to four times higher performance than Free5GC when it comes to processor usage, while RAM, disk, and network usage did not show significant insight when comparing the projects. Based on the aforementioned studies, Open5GS was chosen for the Experimental Test Bed (depicted in Figure 1). For this Test Bed, a Kubernetes Cluster (version 1.31) was created on a server with 128 CPU Cores, 1000GB RAM, and Ubuntu 22.04.4 LTS as the operating system. Furthermore, the Kube Prometheus stack was deployed to collect data from the Kepler instance [15] and monitor resource usage (CPU, memory) of the network functions.

As a traffic generator, my5G-RANTester [23] was chosen due to its ability to perform several 5G procedures. It is an open-source gNB/UE emulator, configured in accordance with the Open5GS instance. Using my5G-RANTester, the registration procedure was conducted for a single user in a loop: As soon as the procedure was completed, the user was deregistered and the gNB and UE were terminated. After that, the procedure was performed again. CPU and memory usage for all parts of the 5G CN were collected during both the idle state of the CN (meaning that no procedure was being carried out) and during the registration procedure.

Figure 2: CPU usage per NF in both idle CN state and during registration procedure. MongoDB CPU usage has been scaled down a hundred times for the sake of visibility.

The CPU usage results (depicted in Figure 2) show a disproportionate amount of CPU resources being used by the MongoDB database [24] compared to the 5G network functions. The increase of CPU usage during the procedure can be observed in almost every network function, with the most significant increases occurring for the AMF, AUSF, PCF, SMF, UDM, and UDR network functions.

When comparing the total usage of CPU resources by all network functions and the MongoDB database (individual values seen in Figure 2), it can be observed that the use of CPU resources of all network functions is a fraction of the CPU resources that the MongoDB database consumes. The MongoDB database consumed over 58 times as many CPU resources during the procedure as all the network functions combined, and over 126 times as much when the network was in the idle state (when no procedures were being performed).

Figure 3 presents the memory usage results, where again a disproportionate resource usage of MongoDB and network functions can be seen. In this case, the difference in memory usage between idle and procedure states is minor. The cumulative memory usage of all network functions (individual values seen in Figure 3) is surpassed by the MongoDB memory usage by

Figure 3: Memory usage per NF in both idle CN state and during registration procedure. MongoDB memory usage has been scaled down ten times for the sake of visibility.

36.84% in the idle state and by 28.16% in the procedure state. The power consumption, which can be seen in Figure 4, differs from the resource usage results. Once again, the MongoDB database uses up to 14 times as much power as individual network functions (such as the UPF network function) in the idle state. However, the average power usage of all network functions (see Figure 4) exceeds the average power used by the MongoDB database both when idle and when performing a procedure by 49.8% and 59.28%, respectively.

In conclusion, the results show that the MongoDB database is responsible for the majority of resources used by the Open5GS instance, both in the idle state and when performing a procedure. In total, the MongoDB instance surpassed the CPU usage of all network functions combined by a factor of 58 during the registration procedure and by a factor of 126 when the network was idle. However, metrics such as average power usage of individual pods provided by Kepler are more lenient toward the MongoDB database. Power usage still indicates that the database consumes a disproportionate number of resources, surpassing some network functions' usage by a factor of 14 in the idle state, but the combined power usage of all network functions was greater than MongoDB's power consumption in both states.

Figure 4: Power usage per NF in both idle CN state and during registration procedure.

Although 3GPP does not specify any technology to fulfill the UDR’s data storage functionality (as defined in [25]), based on the resource usage results, in resource-constrained infrastructure environments, an alternative database should be considered for 5G CN deployment, as MongoDB has proven to consume a disproportionately large amount of resources compared to the rest of Open5GS network functions.

The results presented in this section show the difference in both resource (CPU, Memory) and energy consumption by the 5G CN in "Idle" and "Procedure" states. The increase in resource and energy usage between the states is attributed to the CN performing the UE registration procedure for a single user. Barring the limits of Open-Source CN implementations, shown in [20], where the authors showcase a limit of simultaneously connected UEs in Open5GS, Free5GC, and OpenAirInterface, we can expect an additional increase for each subsequent user for which the procedure will be carried out. The impact of carrying out the registration procedure for multiple users on the energy consumption of the 5G Core Network can be the subject of future work, which should also take into account different user arrival models.

4. 6G Architecture Enhancements

This section presents a set of architectural enablers selected as the most promising for a sustainable 6G system, clustered based on the part of the network where they can be applied. Specifically, the section begins by discussing architectural enablers for energy-efficient AI deployment across the network, then explores specific enhancements in the core and RAN, core-RAN interactions, and the integration of compute resources, particularly at the edge.

4.1. AI for networks

6G networks operate in highly heterogeneous environments, where interconnected devices and nodes across multiple layers share resources. This creates intricate dependencies and poses significant challenges in efficiently orchestrating resources while ensuring sustainable and energy-efficient network operations. Dynamic and stochastic factors, such as user mobility, varying channel conditions, and evolving traffic patterns, add further complexity to decision-making within these networks [26]. As a result, vast amounts of data are continuously generated, requiring real-time processing to optimize network operation and performance. Beyond network-related data, application-specific data must also be shared and processed across various devices and nodes to enable intelligent features of advanced 6G applications. Effectively managing this complexity calls for scalable and resilient network architectures that dynamically adjust to demand fluctuations and unforeseen failures without excessive energy consumption.

Central to this effort is the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) for resource orchestration and decision-making throughout the various layers of the referenced 6G network architecture [26]. Unlike traditional rule-based methods and closed-form solutions, AI is a powerful tool that offers adaptability, flexibility, and scalability. By effectively navigating vast state-action spaces, AI delivers real-time, near-optimal solutions to complex optimization problems, making it essential to tackle the dynamicity and evolving nature of 6G networks [27]. Distributed AI is particularly well-suited for 6G due to its decentralized and modular deployment of AI agents. Specifically, distributed AI allows for a divide-and-conquer strategy to managing cross-domain environments while simultaneously offering a comprehensive overview of the underlying network conditions. Training occurs in a distributed and collaborative manner, facilitating continuous learning and adaptation across differ-

ent network layers. This approach supports sustainability in several ways; a key summary of which is as follows, though this list is not exhaustive.

- *Environmental aspects:* Distributing intelligence across multiple nodes and processing data closer to the source reduces the need for large amounts of data to be transmitted while alleviating single points of failure. This enables scalable and resilient network operations, minimizing energy consumption and signaling overhead from a communication perspective. Nevertheless, a careful balance must be struck to ensure that the local processing at battery and resource-constrained devices remains energy-efficient.
- *Social aspects:* Distributed AI enables intelligent services even in remote or underserved areas, enhancing accessibility and bridging the digital divide. The deployment of distributed AI agents protects sensitive information, respecting the need for privacy preservation and fostering trustworthiness from the users' perspective. Last, the decentralized approach minimizes the risk of data breaches, enhancing security while empowering users with advanced and reliable services.
- *Economical aspects:* Decentralized deployment of AI models reduces reliance on centralized data centers and costly infrastructure by distributing computational loads closer to end users. This approach not only enhances scalability and eliminates single points of failure but also unlocks new functionalities that drive innovation and open up new revenue streams for service providers. However, effective AI/ML lifecycle management and automation tools are crucial to streamlining AI model deployment, ensuring efficient updates, monitoring, and optimization of models across decentralized deployments [28].

4.1.1. *Energy-efficient Resource Management for Distributed AI Operations*

Although AI is recognized as a key component of 6G networks, driving sustainability, additional network enhancements are essential to ensure its seamless integration while addressing the potential tradeoffs discussed earlier. In this subsection, we focus on the critical challenge of enabling energy-efficient, distributed AI training and inference on battery- and resource-constrained user devices. This approach aligns with the environmental sustainability tradeoffs associated with AI, emphasizing the need for intelligent resource management to optimize energy usage while maintaining AI model

performance. This problem has been extensively studied in the literature under various distributed learning architectures (e.g., traditional [29–31] and hierarchical federated learning [32, 33]) and wireless multiple access schemes (e.g., orthogonal [29, 32] and non-orthogonal [30, 31, 33]), with corresponding solutions proposed for power control, user clustering, and subchannel allocation. Nevertheless, to the best of the authors’ knowledge, the approach presented in this work is the first to leverage distributed optimization techniques, as opposed to conventional centralized methods that are often difficult to scale and implement in real-time scenarios.

As an example of a possible AI-based optimization towards a more sustainable 6G, the significant impact of proper radio resource management on distributed AI operations is examined in the following, along with a modeling and solution to the problem. A comparative analysis is also conducted, contrasting distributed AI model training with and without the implementation of radio resource allocation strategies.

Figure 5: High-level overview of the wireless Hierarchical Federated Learning (HFL) network used as a proof-of-concept for energy-efficient resource management for distributed AI.

Consider a wireless Hierarchical Federated Learning (HFL) network, as

shown in Figure 5, where multiple users are distributed among several edge servers for collaborative model training. The users associated with the same edge server transmit their local models over the same time and frequency resources by multiplexing through the power-domain Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access (NOMA) technique. The joint problem of user association and up-link transmission power allocation is formulated as a non-cooperative game in satisfaction form [34], aiming to achieve a tradeoff between training model accuracy, transmission time, and energy consumption for the users in a distributed manner.

The solution concept pursued is the so-called Satisfaction Equilibrium (SE) point, where each end user’s minimum acceptable tradeoff value is satisfied, for both accuracy, time, and energy consumption. The SE point is determined by a Reinforcement Learning (RL) algorithm. The users act as agents that explore their action space, i.e., possible associations and transmission power levels, by observing their achieved tradeoff value, which is provided as feedback from the cloud server. Furthermore, the concept of the Minimum Efficient Satisfaction Equilibrium (MESE) is introduced, which aims to simultaneously minimize the aggregated energy cost of the users while maintaining the acceptable tradeoff. In this context, the determination of the MESE is achieved through the application of the Best Response Dynamics (BRD) algorithm, which leverages the principles of binary search [35].

To quantify the reduction in energy consumption achieved by the radio resource allocation solution within the overall HFL process, the following solutions are also compared: (a) Satisfaction Equilibrium (SE), where a target accuracy-time-energy tradeoff is achieved; (b) Minimum Efficient SE (MESE), which ensures SE while minimizing energy costs; (c) Random Association, where user associations and transmission powers are randomly determined; (d) Closest Server, where users are associated with their nearest server, and power allocation is optimized to achieve SE; and (e) Closest Server MESE, where the same setup targets MESE.

The simulation setup used for experimentation is as follows. We consider a wireless HFL network arranged within a circular area of a 300 m radius. 3 edge servers are randomly positioned along the perimeter of the circular area, and 10 users are uniformly distributed within the area. The total network bandwidth is 10 MHz and the maximum transmission power of each user is 1 W. For the implementation of the HFL procedure, we consider 6 local model updates, 10 edge model updates, and 100 overall HFL iterations. The training learning rate is 10^{-3} , and the data size of the local model parameters

Figure 6: Mean energy consumption reduction and percentage reduction from worst-case achieved by the designed resource allocation solution (i.e., MESE), when compared against other baseline solutions (i.e., SE, random, and closest server).

is 28.1 Kbits. The MNIST dataset is used, and the 60000 total samples are equally divided among the users following in a non-independently Identically Distributed (non-IID) manner by ensuring that no individual user possesses samples of all classes included in the dataset. The simulation setup for both the wireless network and the FL process is based on established works from existing literature [36, 37].

Figure 6 illustrates the mean energy consumption of the users in each of the studied scenarios, along with the percentage difference from the baseline case of "Random Association", where none of the optimization mechanisms is applied. The introduction of any of the proposed mechanisms results in a significant reduction in energy consumption, thereby enhancing the sustainability of the distributed AI process. Notably, the "Closest Server MESE" scenario achieves up to a 90% reduction in energy consumption, highlighting the importance of selecting an appropriate radio resource optimization strategy. The proposed mechanisms, through their efficient management of resources, lead to substantial improvements in energy efficiency, demonstrating their capability to reduce operational costs and environmental impact. The results highlight the potential of these approaches to support more sustainable and energy-efficient distributed AI systems, offering a significant advantage over conventional solutions that lack such optimization.

4.2. Core network enhancements

In this subsection, we discuss architectural enhancements that could be applied to the 6G CN to foster the 6G system’s sustainability.

A common understanding in the industry is that network simplification is correlated with achieving higher sustainability. Accordingly, in the following, we discuss possible changes to the modular design of the CN towards achieving increased simplification and sustainability. The proper design of the 6G CN requires careful selection of the number of NFs and their boundaries. This requires deciding on what functions and features should be consolidated in a single NF and what functions or features should be distributed in more than one NFs. This choice defines the level of granularity over which the NFs are designed. It is important to understand the impact of this NF granularity level when designing the NFs in 6G CNs.

A coarse-grained design of 6G NFs or modules minimizes the number of components involved in executing system procedures. This leads to lower signaling overhead between NFs, faster execution times due to fewer elements in the execution path, and simplified state consistency management among the participating NFs. However, this design trade-off comes at the cost of reduced deployment flexibility, as larger NFs are harder to distribute across different physical locations. It also complicates fault isolation and limits scalability, as coarser modules cannot be independently scaled like their fine-grained counterparts, which allows for more precise resource control.

In contrast to the 5G core control plane, which is structured as a set of interacting NFs, where each NF is responsible for the execution of a certain procedure or task, a new control plane design, proposed in [38], suggests consolidating each system procedure into a single NF. For example, the UE registration process, which in 5G spans multiple NFs such as Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF), Authentication Server Function (AUSF), Policy Control Function (PCF), Network Repository Function (NRF), Unified Data Management (UDM), and Unified Data Repository (UDR), is restructured into a unified *UE Registration NF*. This approach benefits from shorter execution times and reduced signaling, but at the expense of reduced placement flexibility and limited independent scaling, as discussed earlier.

On the other hand, the design of the 5G User Plane Function (UPF), which consolidates many user plane functions and tasks, could be revisited to follow a more fine-grained design that separates different tasks into different modules that can be managed and scaled independently, leading to more cost and energy-efficient operations. One modular UPF design is shown

in Figure 7, where the Control Plane is kept intact while the UPF is split into four different modules. The first module, called the Ingress Steering Module (ISM), takes care of steering incoming packets to the right User Plane Module. Given that the UPF may need to handle an imbalanced distribution of uplink and downlink traffic within the Core Network, the modular design recognizes one function for each direction, i.e., Uplink Module (ULM) and Downlink Module (DLM). This design would enable independent resource allocation for each traffic direction, allowing for scalability based on demand. Finally, the UPF is required to perform specific functions on demand, such as Lawful Intercept, across multiple locations for a limited period. For such a scenario, On-Demand Modules (ODMs), such as Lawful Intercept Module, are introduced to be triggered independently from the UPF, ensuring efficient resource allocation and optimized processing capacity. Such a design is expected to improve the scalability and energy efficiency of the UPF, but it may introduce overhead in the form of increased processing latency when packets traverse a chain of modular UPFs. A detailed analysis is required to quantify these gains and trade-offs; however, this is left for future work.

Figure 7: Modular UPF Design.

4.3. RAN enhancements

Enabling flexibility and interoperability at the RAN level requires architectural solutions that disaggregate functionalities into different entities,

Figure 8: Cell-free RAN network, with several radio units (RUs), two distributed units (DUs), and one centralized unit (CU).

moving away from the monolithic solutions of legacy networks such as distributed RAN (D-RAN), which is currently the most widely deployed legacy network. Such an architecture, where all baseband processing is co-located with the radio units, results in an unscalable and cost-inefficient network, incapable of satisfying the stringent user demands. More flexible, scalable, and [energy-efficient](#) deployments arise from the separation of functionalities into multiple entities and the consequent centralization of baseband processing. For that, functional splits define which entity implements which part of the RAN stack. Compared to a fully distributed architecture, centralizing baseband functions results in a decrease in energy consumption [39].

Cell-free MIMO [40] is a radio interface technology that relies on joint processing of signals from geographically distributed access points, and aims to reduce the large data rate variations across the network area and therefore provide uniformly good service. Joint processing is only possible in centralized RAN deployments, where baseband functionalities are centralized. Therefore, cell-free massive MIMO is seen as one of the potential keystone technologies of 6G. In terms of functional splits, a low-layer split (LLS), where most of the baseband functions are centralized, is crucial for the practical implementation of scalable and efficient cell-free networks.

Figure 8 depicts a disaggregated RAN network supporting cell-free massive MIMO. In this case, functionalities are divided into radio units (RUs), which perform low physical layer functions, distributed units (DUs) imple-

menting lower-layer processing, and centralized units (CUs), which handle higher-layer processing. Such a 3-layer split, with fully virtualized fronthaul and cloud resources, has been shown to improve user rates without increasing the end-to-end energy consumption, compared to a cellular solution with small-cells [41]. Other implementations consider two entities, with a low-layer split in which radio units implement the physical layer, while higher-layer functions are centrally managed by a centralized unit [40].

4.4. RAN-CN Interactions

The control plane signaling between the core network and the RAN has traditionally been done with [point-to-point](#) communication. In 5G networks, the Radio Access Network (RAN) interacts with the Core Network (CN) through the N2 interface, always mediated by the Access and Mobility Function (AMF). This means that any communication between the CN and RAN must pass through the AMF.

[After the introduction of SBA in the 5G CN, there has been interest in also introducing a service-based interface for the RAN to CN interface \[42\].](#)

The N2 interface facilitates various essential functions, including PDU Session Management, UE Context Management, UE Mobility Management, Paging, transport of Non-Access Stratum (NAS) messages, and NG Interface Management. The N2 interface utilizes the Next Generation Application Protocol (NGAP) for communication. NGAP [43] packets are encapsulated within IP and Stream Control Transmission Protocol (SCTP), which are widely used protocols found in various specifications beyond 3GPP.

To ensure a seamless transition from 5G to 6G, the interaction between the Radio Access Network (RAN) and Core Network (CN) must meet the following key requirements:

- The RAN-CN interaction in 6G should allow for a smooth migration from 5G, ensuring continued support for existing 5G services.
- The interaction should accommodate the needs of both existing 5G services and emerging 6G services, including their unique requirements.
- The RAN-CN interaction should be adaptable to various RAN deployment models and architectures.
- The interaction should prioritize efficiency in terms of latency, payload size, reliability, availability, and resilience.

Three primary options are being considered for the RAN-CN Control Plane (CP) interaction in 6G [44]:

1. The 6G RAN continues to communicate with the AMF (or its 6G equivalent) using the NGAP protocol. The RAN retains its ASN.1 encoded interfaces, and the 6G AMF serves as a central point of contact for interactions between the RAN and other CN functions.
2. A Service-Based Interface (SBI) is introduced between the 6G CN and RAN. This allows the 6G RAN to directly expose and consume services from the CN, eliminating the need for a dedicated gateway function.
3. This approach combines the advantages of both the evolutionary and service-based approaches. It introduces a service-based interaction alongside the existing NGAP interface, minimizing disruption to existing point-to-point interactions and avoiding duplication of functionality.

These options offer different trade-offs in terms of complexity, performance, and compatibility with existing 5G infrastructure. An analysis of these options is presented in Table 1.

Option 1, which utilizes the AMF as a central point of contact for all RAN-CN communication, closely resembles the existing 5G solution. This approach offers a smooth migration path from 5G to 6G, as both generations would rely on similar communication mechanisms. Additionally, during a gNB handover, only the AMF needs to be informed of the change in active and idle states, simplifying the process. While Option 1 leverages existing infrastructure, it doesn't preclude potential protocol enhancements. For example, the NGAP protocol could be refined, and the underlying SCTP protocol could be upgraded or replaced to improve efficiency and scalability. These enhancements would further streamline communication and enhance the efficiency of the RAN-CN interaction.

Option 2 proposes a consolidated framework for both RAN and CN, encompassing core functions such as user registration, service discovery, and access authorization. This approach aims to optimize communication by eliminating the AMF proxy, potentially leading to reduced latency in RAN-CN interactions. However, this design necessitates robust security enhancements for all CN NFs. Additionally, the increased interactions with CN NFs present a more complex testing and integration landscape. Furthermore, the lack of inherent support for 5G-to-6G interoperability necessitates the

Option 1	Option 2	Option 3
Features		
The proposed architecture employs a direct communication paradigm between RAN and CN, facilitated by the 6G AMF acting as a central intermediary. This design leverages existing, well-established architectural principles and interfaces, ensuring a robust and validated approach.	The proposed architecture facilitates a direct, service-oriented communication paradigm between RAN and CN NFs. Both 6G RAN and CN NFs expose their capabilities to each other, enabling seamless interaction through RESTful APIs over the SBI interface.	The architecture leverages existing 5G communication support through the AMF, utilizing established peer-to-peer interfaces. Simultaneously, it enables direct RAN-CN NF communication for new 6G services. This approach ensures backward compatibility and seamless integration of new capabilities.
Pros and cons		
Leverages the inherent security of the clear separation between RAN and CN. This approach naturally facilitates 5G to 6G interoperability and migration. However, the current N2 interface may require enhancements to better accommodate cloud-native architectures in the 6G era.	While this approach potentially reduces system latency by eliminating a CN NF proxy hop, it introduces complexities in security management due to the lack of clear domain separation and the presence of multiple UE anchor points in the CN. This necessitates extensive standardization and testing efforts to ensure robust security and operational stability.	This approach reduces the AMF's workload by eliminating proxy tasks for non-communication services. However, it necessitates increased standardization efforts to ensure seamless support for both SBI and P2P interfaces.

Table 1: Summary of RAN-CN interaction options for 6G [44]

development of supplementary mechanisms to ensure a seamless transition between generations.

Option 3 presents a synergistic approach, integrating aspects of Option

1 and Option 2. This strategy leverages the existing AMF infrastructure for established services while introducing SBI for emerging 6G services, such as sensing applications. Given that 5G primarily focuses on UE-related services, this solution ensures backward compatibility and facilitates a gradual migration from 5G to 6G, but only for existing 5G services.

4.5. Compute/edge integration

The need for ultra-low latency services requires moving computational capacity towards the edge of the network. This approach has been followed in 5G, with multiple different approaches such as ETSI MEC or 3GPP Edge Application framework. The well-known edge computing (EC) concept helps 5G networks to achieve low propagation delays between the communication end-points, while also enabling the network to obtain cost savings by keeping local traffic local. 6G networks will follow a similar approach with respect to the use of the edge, albeit with a higher importance for the network. The concept of Compute Continuum, where the computing capacities of the network span from the UE or its very close proximity (extreme edge), to the edge computing near the user (far edge) to the cloud, has evolved towards the Connected Collaborative Computing or 3C networks ecosystem, spanning over the entire computing continuum, through the connectivity infrastructure, data management, and applications.

The 3C concept requires novel approaches towards the integration of different domains into a single computing infrastructure for the operator. This concept is supported by novel technologies for the integration of new resources in the computing continuum, such as multi-cloud federation, integration of end-devices in the computing distributed architecture of the operator, management of virtual infrastructure (highlighting key open source initiatives such as the Sylva project) and also new research and developments in the management of all this complex environment.

The control, integration, and management of this complex ecosystem are [also being](#) engineered in the GSMA Operator Platform project, where operators are trying to come up with a common vision on how to integrate all the different computing resources under a common infrastructure umbrella.

Once the 3C concept becomes a reality, as expected for 6G networks, one of the remaining challenges in this space will be how to better make use of these resources so that the network can trade off between computing capacity and network delay. This is the objective of the Integration of Network and Compute (INC), designed for coordinated optimization.

When UE accesses services deployed in compute sites, it faces strict network and compute requirements. Traditional Edge Computing (EC) deploys multiple continuously running service instances across different locations, with instance selection primarily driven by UE proximity to minimize latency. However, this conventional approach has drawbacks. Proximity-based selection can overwhelm compute resources near the UE, while maintaining constantly running instances leads to resource inefficiency.

The INC approach represents a paradigm shift from traditional EC by implementing coordinated management of network and compute resources to enhance service placement efficiency and reduce energy usage. As shown in Figure 9, the architecture features a Communication Service Provider (CSP) handling network connectivity, while Cloud Providers manage compute resources at edge and central cloud locations. These two entities, i.e., CSP and Cloud Providers, may operate independently. The INC framework treats network and compute resources as an integrated system under unified processes, utilizing an INC functionality for coordinated optimization. This functionality aggregates network performance metrics from the CSP (such as delay and throughput parameters) and compute resource information from cloud providers (including CPU/GPU and memory availability) through standardized interfaces. Based on these metrics, the INC functionality optimizes application placement decisions to meet both network and compute requirements, as well as to reduce energy consumption. The process typically involves selecting an appropriate compute site (which then handles local node selection), followed by coordinated deployment requests to both the compute site and the CSP to ensure proper application hosting and traffic management with guaranteed Quality of Service (QoS).

As shown in Figure 10, the generic procedure for the INC approach is as follows:

- **Metric Collection:** The INC functionality gathers both network and compute metrics that are considered UE-independent. Network metrics primarily focus on the delay between the access network and different compute sites, while compute metrics pertain to resource availability at the compute sites across various edge and cloud providers.
- **Request Formulation:** The application generates a service deployment request, detailing the necessary network and compute requirements, which is then submitted to the INC functionality.

Figure 9: High-level architecture for Integrated Network and Compute.

- **Collection of UE-Specific Metrics:** The INC functionality gathers metrics specific to the target UE, such as the delay between the target UE and the access network.
- **Decision-Making:** The INC functionality determines the optimal target compute site for service deployment by evaluating the application's network and compute requirements alongside the collected metrics. Energy consumption is also considered in the selection process.
- **Decision Enforcement:** The INC functionality issues a request to enforce the decision, instructing the target compute site to deploy the service and coordinating with the network for QoS enforcement and traffic steering to the selected compute site.

5. Intent based management

The integration of intent-based APIs into network management systems represents a transformative approach to improving environmental sustainability. Using high-level abstractions and automation, intent-based APIs enable networks to operate more efficiently, reducing energy consumption

Figure 10: Call flow for Integrated Network and Compute execution.

while maintaining performance. Intent-based networking shifts the focus from low-level, manual configuration to high-level, declarative policies that define the desired outcomes of the network. For example, an intent might state, "Ensure low-latency connectivity for critical applications while minimizing energy usage." This abstraction simplifies network management and ensures that energy efficiency is embedded as a core objective in network operations.

Environmental sustainability is a critical consideration in modern network design, driven by the growing energy demands of data centers, edge computing, and 5G/6G networks. Intent-based APIs contribute to energy efficiency by enabling dynamic resource allocation and optimization, for example, prioritizing renewable energy sources. By aligning network behavior with environmental sustainability goals, intent-based APIs help reduce the carbon footprint of digital infrastructure.

Live monitoring tools (e.g., presented in Section III-B) collect real-time data on network performance, energy consumption, and environmental conditions. When deviations from the intent are detected, a reconciliation loop can be configured to trigger automated actions to realign the network with its goals. Operators federated networks and the integration of the cloud contin-

uum are critical enablers of energy sustainability in intent-based networking. These concepts allow for seamless coordination of resources across distributed environments, optimizing energy usage on a global scale. An important element of the cloud continuum approach is the resource layer, which contains resource-oriented functions. Among these functions is DCME (Data Centre Monitoring Engine), which collects and evaluates real-time telemetry from each data center, i.e., energy consumption, performance, and reliability.

6. Comparison of enhancements with 5G

This section focus on the proposed enhancements and their advantages as well as challenges over 5G system, cf. Table 2.

Enhancement	Advantages	Challenges
Compute/edge integration (INC)	Unlike 5G, which only focuses on optimizing network performance targets, INC also optimizes compute performance targets.	This requires the acquisition of compute resource information through standardized interfaces.
Intent-based Management (IBM)	5G networks are complex to manage, especially in dynamic environments. IBM automates and adapts configurations using intent-based control loops to ensure performance goals are met.	To ensure interoperability, intents should be standardized in a way that is not ambiguous or abstract

RAN enhancement with cell-free massive MIMO.	Large numbers of coordinated access points distributed in the network area to achieve seamless coverage and increased spectral efficiency, with higher levels of scalability and adaptability.	Increased signal processing complexity, and more stringent coordination requirements among the access points.
Energy-efficient resource management for distributed AI operations	The resource allocation problem is formulated and solved as a non-cooperative game in satisfaction form, enabling distributed and low-complexity decision-making that preserves scalability, while ensuring that each player meets its quality of service (QoS) requirements without exhausting system resources.	The proposed distributed decision-making solution requires signaling and coordination, as local resource allocation decisions must be exchanged among players to reach the system's equilibrium point.
Modular User Plane Function Design	The modularization of the UPF enhances deployment flexibility and simplifies the management of scaling functions up or down. As a result, it enables more energy-efficient operation through improved resource utilization driven by enhanced scalability.	When packets traverse a chain of modularized UPFs, some increase in latency is expected compared to a monolithic design. In addition, managing a larger number of functions and maintaining consistent packet processing state across these modules adds complexity to the system design.

Table 2: Comparison of the proposed enhancements, advantages and posed challenges with respect to the 5GS

7. Conclusion

This paper explores the concept of a sustainable 6G architecture, focusing on environmental, social, and economic sustainability. It highlights the need to move beyond traditional performance KPIs and incorporate KVis such as trustworthiness, inclusivity, and sustainability as a design factor for the network. The paper explores several key enablers for achieving this goal, including the integration of AI for efficient resource orchestration and decision-making across network layers, promoting energy efficiency, and enhancing service accessibility. It also advocates for a modular architecture, where NFs are grouped into modules that can be deployed and scaled independently, enabling flexibility and cost-effectiveness. The paper further introduces the INC framework, which aims to optimize service placement by coordinating network and compute resources, minimizing latency and energy consumption. Additionally, it highlights the potential of Intent-Based Management, an approach that leverages high-level abstractions and automation to enable networks to operate more efficiently, reducing energy consumption while maintaining performance. The paper also examines the need for enhancements in both the RAN and Core Network to support a sustainable 6G architecture. Further, the paper explores different options for RAN-CN interaction, including the use of SBI and hybrid approaches. Finally, the paper discusses the integration of edge computing and the concept of a Compute Continuum, where computing resources are distributed across the network, from the user device to the cloud. This approach aims to address the need for ultra-low latency services and optimize resource utilization.

Acknowledgment

This work has been funded by the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Hexa-X-II project (grant agreement No. 101095759).

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